

A RENEWED VISION OF MARKET DEFINITION'S IMPORTANCE

COMPETITION LAW IN
THE COLLECTIVE INTEREST

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A Renewed Vision of Market Definition's Importance: Competition Law in the Collective Interest*

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Abstract

This working paper presents a renewed vision of the role of market definition in competition law, emphasizing its importance in safeguarding the collective interest. This paper argues that market definition is crucial for ensuring the legitimacy of competition law enforcement. While often brushed aside as a technical or procedural step, this paper contends that market definition has normative value, aligning competition law enforcement with its overarching goal of protecting the collective interest. By drawing a market's boundaries, authorities can illustrate how their enforcement activities are focused on the collective interest, the public good, and evidence their competence to act and apply competition law (rather than other areas of law or regulation). Furthermore, the paper explores the boundaries between competition law and other legal frameworks, such as intellectual property and digital markets regulation, to illustrate why market definition remains a distinct and vital tool in competition cases. Through this fresh perspective, the paper intends to address calls to abandon market definition, while contributing to ongoing debates about the scope and purpose of competition law in a rapidly evolving economic and societal landscape.

* This is work in progress. Comments are very welcome and encouraged.

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I. Introduction

At a time when competition policy's relationship with pressing social concerns such as labour standards, sustainability, and democracy are back on the radar, debate about the (ir)relevance of market definition in competition law appears rather unglamorous. It is not uncommon for a discussion about the scope of 'the relevant market' in a competition law case to be dismissed as a purely technical matter. And yet, this debate strikes at the heart of what competition law is meant to achieve. This article contends that market definition can contribute to the legitimacy of competition law enforcement, by externalising that the law is used to safeguard the collective interest.

Markets have a specific meaning in competition law, building on – but distinct from – economic theory. There is no single market for competition law purposes, just as there is no universal 'economic market'. Although it generally refers to the arena where demand and supply meet, the 'market' concept has a different meaning depending on the purpose for which it is used and the phenomenon being studied. Markets are drawn to 'isolate certain kinds of activities from others in order to make sense and think creatively about what we observe'.² In competition law, the relevant market translates economic concepts into a legal device, upon which competition authorities and courts can rely to solve a problem of competition law. The delineation of a relevant market is a first step in most competition law cases, as it provides the boundaries within which to understand competition between economic actors and the products they offer.

The provisions of competition law in the European Union are found in Articles 101 and 102 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, as well as in the EU Merger Regulation. Although none of these provisions explicitly require market definition,³ it plays a role in the analysis of conduct under each of them. It aids in establishing market power and in assessing the economic context and effects of a practice. Despite (or perhaps because of) its prevalence in competition law enforcement, market definition has been the subject of debate between scholars and practitioners around the world. Critics in the United States of America particularly focused on the limitations in using market definition as a step to establish market power (which is a condition for the application of most of the rules), while in the European Union the lengthy and resource-intensive character of the exercise has led experts to disfavour market definition.⁴ This article refutes the suggestion that market definition should be abandoned. It argues that, in

² Paul Geroski, 'Thinking Creatively about Markets' (1998) 16 *International Journal of Industrial Organization* 692.

³ This is the case in some but not all jurisdictions, such as for example Brazil, see Magali Eben and Viktoria Robertson, 'Digital market definition in the European Union, United States, and Brazil: Past, Present, and Future' (2022) 18(2) *Journal of Competition Law and Economics* 420-423.

⁴ See references in n 9 below.

addition to the usefulness of having a demarcated scope within which to assess conduct and its impact, identifying the relevant market in a competition case can serve a normative purpose.

This article argues that establishing the scope of a 'market' is not merely a procedural requirement but a condition for the legitimacy of competition law enforcement in its substance. Practically, if there is consensus on the need to delineate competitive pressures in competition cases, then having robust and reliable means to do so is crucial.⁵ But the legitimacy of enforcement extends beyond the need for a robust *method* to delineate markets, providing the answer to the more fundamental question whether we even need to establish a market in the first place. This article claims that the mere activity of market delineation – regardless of the method used – contributes to the legitimacy of competition law enforcement. Competition law belongs to a set of policies and laws which address failures in the market mechanism.⁶ Connecting its enforcement to the 'market' – the object which cases are meant to address – is an important means for ensuring its internal coherence, and for addressing (at least some) claims of 'arbitrary' decision-making by authorities.⁷ Market definition can help evidence that competition law is enforced in line with its collective interest aims, important for its internal legitimacy and to keep it distinct from other areas of law which may apply to the same actors and conduct.

This article contributes to the scholarship through an articulation of the added value of market definition, despite existing methodological challenges, and in doing so responds to calls to abandon market definition. It also contributes to the discussion about the boundaries between competition law and other areas of law which may apply to the same actors for similar conduct. It fills a much-needed gap in the scholarship on the normative justifications for market definition.

⁵ Market definition can contribute to the practical as well as the substantive legitimacy of competition law enforcement. As already aptly described by Sousa Ferro, market definition provides practical legitimacy to enforcement by providing an 'objective means' to delineate competitive pressures in a 'predictable and reasonably accurate' manner. See Miguel Sousa Ferro, *Market Definition in EU Competition Law* (Edward Elgar Publishing, 2019) 30. In this piece, however, the focus is on the substantive legitimacy for competition law rather than the practical legitimacy.

⁶ Niamh Dunne, *Competition Law and Economic Regulation: Making and Managing Markets* (Cambridge University Press 2015), 6, 9 and 33; SG Breyer, 'Antitrust, Deregulation and the Newly Liberated Marketplace' (1987) 75 *California Law Review* 1006.

⁷ Christopher Decker, *Economics and the Enforcement of European Competition Law* (Edward Elgar 2009) 164; See, for an interesting analysis of objectivity and legitimacy in using other scientific sources than economics, Vinicius Klein, 'Economic Arguments In Competition Law Reasoning After Digitalization' [working paper April 2024] available on ssrn: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4782793.

Section II introduces the key argument of this article: that the definition of a relevant market - and subsequent reference to the market in the substantive analysis - contributes to the legitimacy of competition law enforcement. The section first discusses, generally, the theory for the legitimacy of the application of a specific law and intervention by a specific authority. It then sets out how the 'market' can be the expression of this legitimacy in the enforcement of competition law. Since the underlying assumption of Section II (and the article as a whole) is that competition law protects the collective interest, Section III provides support for this assumption. Competition law is not the only law or regulation which is adopted or enforced by reference to the market. Section IV therefore sets out the differences between various ways in which the market can be referred to in laws, illustrating why these other laws may not need market definition as a matter of legitimacy. The Section refers to laws protecting individual interests as well as laws meant to protect the market. It uses intellectual property laws and the Digital Markets Act as examples. It also, briefly, reflects on 'by object' conduct and presumptions and evidentiary standards within competition law itself.

This article intends to convince readers of two things. First, that the existing scholarship on market definition misses the point that market definition has value of itself. Second, at a time when there seems to be a crisis about the extent of the competences of competition authorities, the reference to the 'relevant market' as representation of the collective interest may be a way to justify the applicability of competition law.

II. The market as a source of legitimacy

Market definition is an important tool in different jurisdictions across the world, and plays a central role across all provisions of EU competition law. It plays a role in the analysis of anti-competitive agreements (Article 101 TFEU), abuse of dominance (Article 102 TFEU) and mergers (EU Merger Regulation). A relevant market can be used to establish market power, indirectly, by providing a basis for the calculation of market shares. Market definition can also aid in determining that there is an impairment of competition relevant to Articles 101 or 102 TFEU or to the EU Merger Regulation. This author has previously argued that antitrust market definition is useful precisely because it is a method to enable the answer to a question about the feasibility of alleged conduct, the theory of harm and alleged anti-competitive effects.⁸ Prominent scholars have argued against the use of market definition, because of its limitations in establishing

⁸ Magali Eben, 'The Antitrust Market Does Not Exist: Pursuit of Objectivity in a Purposive Process' (2021) 17(3) *Journal of Competition Law and Economics* 586.

market power,⁹ but they overlook its utility beyond that purpose. The definition of the relevant market persists because it provides enforcers with an easy to comprehend method to structure the evidence before them, so that they can answer the questions they were called upon to resolve.¹⁰

This article takes the defence of market definition a step further, reflecting not merely on its utility, but on the reasons it can contribute to the legitimacy of competition law enforcement. Defining a relevant market contributes in two ways: first, by evidencing that the enforcement competition law aligns with its own purpose of safeguarding collective interest, and second, by evidencing that it does not encroach on other legal domains without justification.

A. Substantive legitimacy

This article argues that the definition of a relevant market brings substantive legitimacy to the enforcement of competition law. By representing the protection of the collective, the market serves as a tool to demonstrate that a competition authority is aware of the boundaries of its mandate. To support that claim, this section briefly explores the elements which contribute to make a law, and its enforcement by a specific authority, appear legitimate.

As a starting assumption, the attribution of competences to a competition authority to intervene against certain types of (market power-related) market failures can be justified because it solves a coordination problem. When a competition authority intervenes in economic activities, it acts on behalf of the collective to resolve market failures and address practices which are considered harmful to that collective; it is better placed to do so than individual market participants who may not be able to set aside their own individual interests in determining their conduct. We may all agree that a certain economic ideal is best, but an individual market participant – despite the fact that its commercial knowledge may be superior to the authority – may not be able to transcend its own interests and make a decision which benefits the collective. In this interpretation of Raz’s model of legitimacy, market participants are better off following an

⁹ See extensive debate: Louis Kaplow, ‘Why (Ever) Define Markets’ (2010) 124(2) Harvard Law Review 437; R.S. Markovits, ‘The Inevitable Arbitrariness of Market Definition’ in Richard S. Markovits (ed). *Economics and the Interpretation and Application of U.S. and E.U. Antitrust Law: Volume I* (Springer 2012) 165; Greg J. Werden, ‘Antitrust Needs the Relevant Market’ in Barry Hawk (ed.) *International Antitrust Law and Policy* (Fordham Competition Law 2013); Duncan Cameron, Mark Glick, David Mangum, ‘Good Riddance to Market Definition’ (2012) 57(4) *Antitrust Bulletin* 719; David Glasner and Sean Sullivan, ‘The Logic of Market Definition’ (2020) 83(2) *Antitrust Law Journal* 293; Sean Sullivan, ‘Seven Myths of Market Definition’ (April 2022) *Antitrust Chronicle*.

¹⁰ Eben (n 8 above) 586.

authority than their own reasoning.¹¹ Thus, intervention by an authority is preferred over the (mere) actions of individuals.

Although this answers the question why we might prefer intervention by a public authority, it does not explain why the most appropriate intervention is by a *competition authority* enforcing *competition law*. There are, after all, many different areas of law and corresponding authorities – and we need to understand the boundaries between the different laws to understand the legitimacy of their enforcement.

The legitimacy of intervention by a specific authority – and of that law more generally – can derive from its normative coherence, i.e. from the coherence of the different rules with a particular common value (preferably one generally agreed upon). The enforcement of a set of rules in a specific case will appear legitimate if subjects know the normative principle (the aim) which underpins the law, and the enforcement of the law has a clear relationship with that aim.

Moreover, the objectives of the law can also serve to establish the boundaries with *other* laws and policies. Confirmation that an authority applies its competences in line with the objectives of the law for which it is the enforcer, ensures it follows its legal mandate without intruding in mandate of other authorities or courts, (which could be construed as a type of ‘competence creep’).

Monti has argued that the boundaries of antitrust are a key question to be resolved, suggesting that we need ‘a better conceptual framework to distinguish between the harms protected by competition law and those harms that are not within its purview.’¹² Limitations on the playing field of an authority can come from institutional design,¹³ but in line with Monti’s argument, they are more robust and normatively coherent if they are the result of substantive requirements on authorities when they enforce the law. Two of Monti’s four principles¹⁴ refer to the interest the

¹¹ Raz proposed the ‘normal justification thesis’, according to which authority is justified when it helps individuals better conform to their moral goals or rational reasons than they could do independently. Authority is only justified if its compliance with these reasons ‘is likely to be better than that of its subjects’. J. Raz, ‘Authority, Law, and Morality’ in Joseph Raz, *Ethics in the Public Domain: Essays in the Morality of Law and Politics* 214-215; Scott Hershovitz, ‘Legitimacy, Democracy, and Razian Authority’ (2003) 9(3) *Legal Theory* 201; Timothy Macklem, *Law and Life in Common* (Oxford University Press, 2015) 109; Ben Martin, ‘Raz’s appeal to law’s authority’ (2023) 181 *Philosophical Studies* 267.

¹² Giorgio Monti, ‘The Boundaries of Antitrust in the European Union’ in Oles Andriychuk (ed), *Antitrust and the Bounds of Power: 25 Years On* (Hart Publishing, 2023) 57-58.

¹³ Cf. Amato’s argument in 1997 that ‘if the new premises are to be given their proper development, if antitrust law is truly to be freed from the interference that limits and conditions it, then the creation of an independent Authority to decide on restrictive agreements, abuses and mergers can be seen as the necessary conclusion, ...’ (Giuliano Amato, *Antitrust and the Bounds of Power: The Dilemma of Liberal Democracy in the History of the Market* (Hart Publishing, 1997) 122).

¹⁴ The four principles are: first, the boundaries of antitrust are drawn with reference to the interest the law is designed to protect; second, the conduct has to fulfil the other requirements of the statute; third, the

law is designed to protect: the boundaries of antitrust are to be drawn by reference to the interest the law is designed to protect,¹⁵ and the application of the law should achieve the objective of safeguarding the interests the law protects.¹⁶

At a time when competition authorities are increasingly called upon to consider a wider range of issues in the enforcement of the law, it may be particularly pertinent to establish delimiting factors to their powers (and avoid competence creep¹⁷). Even where the 'social contract' changes, potentially justifying an expansion of the considerations taken into account in the enforcement of competition law,¹⁸ there remains a need for a delimiting factor which distinguishes the substance of competition law from other laws and thus the competences of a competition authority from other authorities, courts, and regulators.¹⁹

This article assumes first, that harm to competition is a substantive element showing that competition law provisions apply;²⁰ and, second, that harm to competition in competition law is about the protection of a collective, rather than individual interests. Thus, the use of competition law by a competition authority to pursue individual interests, particularly where they are covered by other laws, may be illegitimate. This article proposes that the market, representing the protection of the collective, can function as a tool to evidence that a competition authority is aware of and engages with the boundaries on its competences.

application of competition law should always achieve the objective of safeguarding the interests the law protects; and fourth, antitrust law need not apply if the interest protected by antitrust is already safeguarded by another more specific regulatory instrument. (Monti (n 12) above 58-60).

¹⁵ Ibid. 58: he refers to economic welfare (distilled from economics interpretation of the law) and the historical analysis which indicates an interest in keeping markets open.

¹⁶ Ibid. 59.

¹⁷ Weatherill reflected on competence creep when the European union 'exercises competences attributed to it in a manner that unnecessarily interferes with the competences that remain in the hands of the Member States', which damages the formal and social legitimacy of the European Union (S. Weatherill, 'Competence and Legitimacy' in Catherine Barnard and Okeoghene Odudu (eds.) *The Outer Limits of European Union Law* (Hart Publishing, 2009) 17). A similar concern can be raised where competition authorities / law creeps into the field of application of other laws (and competences of other authorities) without normative justification or boundaries. This is a debate worth having, particularly now that competition law is being used to bolster other laws or fill gaps left by other legislators (e.g. GDPR – German Meta case, C-252/21 *Meta Platforms v. Bundeskartellamt*; e.g. French cases on the CDSM directive – see French Competition Authority, Decisions 22-D-13 (June 2022), 21-D-17 (July 2021) and 20-MC-01 (April 2020)). This discussion is outside the scope of this article.

¹⁸ An important point made by Lianos, who views potential changes in the social contract as a justification for the expansion of the goals of and/or interests protected by competition law (see Ioannis Lianos, 'Polycentric Competition Law' (2019) 71(1) *Current Legal Problems* 161).

¹⁹ In this sense, this author agrees with Monti that a proven change in the social contract requires more than a revision of the enforcement of competition law, but 'calls for an overall assessment of all state policies to determine how each is best calibrated' (Monti (n 12) above) 67, own emphasis).

²⁰ Harm to competition can serve a jurisdictional function (when harm to competition in the internal market enables EU institutions to claim jurisdiction over a matter) or a substantive element (showing that provisions of competition law apply), Cf. Okeoghene Odudu, *The Boundaries of EC Competition Law: The Scope of Article 81* (Oxford University Press 2006) 98-103.

B. The market as an essential concept

The market is a foundational concept in competition law, since competition law strives to safeguard the free *market* economy from deleterious distortions.²¹ If competition law is intended to 'manage markets',²² or 'make markets work better',²³ it makes sense for 'the market' to occupy a central place in its enforcement. Since competition law belongs to a set of policies and laws which address failures in the market mechanism,²⁴ connecting its enforcement to the 'market' – the object which cases are meant to address – ensures its legitimacy and can address (at least some) claims of 'arbitrary' decision-making by authorities.²⁵

The requirement of market definition externalises a difference between competition law and other areas of law: that certain conduct is prohibited not (merely) because of its harmful impact on individuals, but because of its impact on a *collective* of economic actors and activities – the 'market'. As is set out in a previous article,²⁶ market definition can be useful to assess the effects of specific conduct. For these effects to be anti-competitive, it is not sufficient that they are felt merely on the price or output of an individual firm ('s product); they have to be felt on the market.²⁷ Competition law protects the 'collective interest' in addition to protecting the interests of specific market participants. In other words, the enforcement of competition law is not undertaken (merely) to repair the damage caused to an individual, but to address damage to a public good – the market.²⁸

If anti-competitive is to be understood as that which harms the market – and thus the collective interest²⁹ – rather than merely harm individuals, it is essential to define what this market is. Market definition enables the identification of the subject of the case, and assess whether the

²¹ Rupperecht Podszun, 'The Arbitrariness of Market Definition and an Evolutionary Concept of Markets' (2016) 61 *The Antitrust Bulletin* 129.

²² Dunne (n 6 above).

²³ European Commission's Directorate-General for Communication, 'Competition. Making Markets Work Better' *The European Union Explained* (2016) 33, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2775/08712>.

²³ Dunne (n 6 above) 6, 9 and 33; Breyer (n 6 above) 1006.

²⁵ Decker (n 7 above) 164.

²⁶ Eben (n 8 above) 586.

²⁷ Thomas B. Nachbar, 'Qualitative market definition' (2023) 109 *Virginia Law Review*, 402–403.

²⁸ Although, it has been argued, that while the goals of antitrust law make it mainly public interest law, individual interests groups may influence the direction of enforcement so that it becomes 'shaped largely by private interests and not by the public interest.' (see Fred S. McChesney and William F. Shughart II (eds), *The Causes and Consequences of Antitrust: The Public-Choice Perspective* (University of Chicago Press 1995) x, 1–3).

²⁹ Which may be impediments to the 'market mechanism' or (narrower) focuses on welfare or total wealth. See, for example, Eleanor M. Fox, 'What is Harm to Competition? Exclusionary Practices and Anticompetitive Effect' (2002) 70 *Antitrust Law Journal* 372.

conduct indeed affects the market, rather than being (unfortunate but not anti-competitive) singular occurrences without repercussions for the collective concerns of market participants.

Over the years, there has been ferocious debate about the meaning of ‘competition’, as well as vocal criticism of the European Commission when it was allegedly ‘protecting competitors’ instead of ‘protecting competition’.³⁰ This critique points to a conceptual difficulty with distinguishing the protection of competition as a ‘public good’, from the protection of individual interests: not only does competition have a variety of meanings but these two understandings may also overlap. Although this debate is unlikely to ever die down, it can be argued that the answer to this conceptual question lies in the market concept: competition law can be distinguished from other areas of law (that protect competitors or consumers) because its *raison d’être* is the market *and* because this market-concept is instrumentalised. These are two cumulative conditions: It would not be enough to merely *refer* to the market in the objective of the law (in recitals, preparatory documents to the law, or in obiter dicta), since other laws may also protect the market indirectly by safeguarding individual interests. Rather, the market needs to function as a working concept. Harm to the market is a vital component of the reasoning in a case – and thus the market is an essential analytical unit.³¹

This article links the ‘market’ with the legitimacy of competition law enforcement, because of the idea that the market represents the ‘collective’. Thus, the underlying assumption is that competition law is about protecting the collective interest. The next section provides support for this assumption.

III. Competition law protects the collective interest

The assumption in this article that competition law first and foremost protects the collective interest. This assumption is supported by the objectives of competition law. Despite disagreement and divergence over time on the specific objectives of competition law, the idea

³⁰ See, e.g., the statements made by the Assistant Attorney General for Antitrust at the US Department of Justice in response to the CFI’s judgment in 2007 upholding the Commission’s infringement decision against Microsoft for abusing its dominant position. B Thomas ‘Statement on European Microsoft Decision’ (Press Release) available at: http://www.usdoj.gov/atr/public/press_releases/2007/226070.htm. A list of similar critics of the European competition law framework can be found in the first footnote of Professor Fox’s article: Eleanor M. Fox, ‘We Protect Competition, You Protect Competitors’ (2003) 26(2) World Competition 149. Despite the Commission’s own assurance that protecting competitors is not the primary goal: Communication from the Commission – Guidance on the Commission’s enforcement priorities in applying Article 82 of the EC Treaty to abusive exclusionary conduct by dominant undertakings (Text with EEA relevance) OJ C 45, 24.2.2009, para 6.

³¹ This does not mean, however, that there is no room for ‘by object’ standards, if desired, insofar as these are premised on presumptions of harm to competition on the market. See section IV.B Laws protecting the market.

that the law pursues a public good remains a constant in most perspectives on the goals of competition law. According to Posner, efficiency is an important social value³², and monopoly a source of significant social costs.³³ Posner deemed that '[s]ince efficiency is an important social value, this ... establishes a prima facie case for having an antitrust policy.'³⁴ Gerber argues that the normative justification for competition law is that 'particular forms or levels of competition are good for society'.³⁵ Other normative justifications for competition law exist, but many focus on the market as an institution achieving a collective benefit. When developing a normative justification for criminal enforcement, Wardhaugh describes the harm done by cartels as harm to the market-institution rather than to individuals. In his words, markets are 'mean[s] of distributive justice', by which is meant that the market is the means through which participants distribute and acquire resources in pursuit of their goals.³⁶

A. The collective interest in competitive markets

The premise underpinning competition policy is that well-functioning markets can achieve benefits for the public – for a larger collective – not just for individual interests. Since Adam Smith there has been a (useful if not perfect) assumption that the common good will be served through 'the voluntary acts of millions of individuals each pursuing [their] own objectives'.³⁷ This assumption carried over to political science's discussion of public interest more broadly, with the ('naïve') presumption that 'the public interest will automatically be served if all men pursue

³² Richard Posner, *Antitrust law* (2nd edn, University of Chicago Press 2001) 2.

³³ *Ibid.* 9.

³⁴ *Ibid.* 2.

³⁵ David Gerber, *Law and Competition in Twentieth Century Europe: Protecting Prometheus* (Oxford University Press 2001) 418. See also Anna Gerbrandy, 'Rethinking Competition Law within the European Economic Constitution' (2019) 57 *Journal of Common Market Studies* 129.

³⁶ Bruce Wardhaugh, 'A normative approach to the criminalisation of cartel activity' (2012) *Legal Studies* 391.

³⁷ Milton Friedman, 'The Invisible Hand' in 'The Business System: A Bicentennial View (1977) 4-5, found in Robert Leeson and Charles G. Palm (eds.) *The Collected Works of Milton Friedman*, Hoover Institution Archives, available at <http://miltonfriedman.hoover.org/objects/57602>; Adam Smith wrote, in Book IV of *The Wealth Of Nations*: 'every individual necessarily labours to render the annual revenue of the society as great as he can. He generally, indeed, neither intends to promote the public interest, nor knows how much he is promoting it. By preferring the support of domestic to that of foreign industry, he intends only his own security; and by directing that industry in such a manner as its produce may be of the greatest value, he intends only his own gain, and he is in this, as in many other cases, led by an invisible hand to promote an end which was no part of his intention. Nor is it always the worse for the society that it was no part of it. By pursuing his own interest he frequently promotes that of the society more effectually than when he really intends to promote it.' (Adam Smith, *The Wealth of Nations*, Book IV Of Systems of Political Economy (originally 1776, Electric Book Company 2001 edition) 593-594; Stavros Makris, 'A Political Economy Approach to Competition Law? The Everlasting Legacy of Adam Smith' [forthcoming, on file with the author].

their own interests'.³⁸ Competitive markets (are assumed to) allocate resources, goods and services, in a societally beneficial manner.

The support for competitive markets has roots in a variety of intellectual and ideological movements, chief among them the belief that competitive market organisation – rather than centralised design – is more appropriate to (efficiently or rationally) address collective problems and achieve the public good.³⁹ Markets are 'fields of organised action':⁴⁰ through the ability of market participants to co-ordinate their actions with that of others without needing to know their identify, the competitive market achieves the best outcome for the whole.⁴¹ Markets are assumed to lead to the most efficient allocation of resources, to the welfare of the whole.

We can leave aside, for the sake of this article, the precise articulation of the societal benefit competition brings,⁴² although as is noted below, such an articulation will be important to fully realise the function of the market put forward in this paper. The debate about the objectives of competition (law) is a vital one but detracts, for the moment, from the main point at hand: that, despite divergences, there is a consensus that competition is (often)⁴³ in the common interest.

Smithian conceptualisations of the competitive market do not assume a totally isolated, self-standing mechanism in which individual interests would naturally achieve outcomes in the interest of the collective. Rather, they achieve these outcomes only because of the institutional (including legal) priors which provide the context in which they can function well. Thus, for markets to achieve the common good, intervention may be needed. If you believe that markets lead to the public good, as long as competition is safeguarded as a necessary condition for their

³⁸ Barry Bozeman, *Public Values and Public Interest: Counterbalancing Economic Individualism* (2007 Georgetown University Press) 85.

³⁹ Christian Frankel, Jossé Ossandón, and Trine Pallesen, 'The Organization of Markets For Collective Concerns and Their Failures' (2019) 48(2) *Economy and Society* 158; Reinhard Bendix, 'Bureaucracy and the Problem of Power' (1945) 5(3) *Public Administration Review* 201; Ludwig von Mises, 'Part 6: The Hampered Market Economy' in Ludwig von Mises/Bettina Bien Greaves (ed.) *Human Action: A Treatise on Economics* (1949) (English translation of *Nationalökonomie* (1940)), Chapter 27, in particular 724, 731; Friedrich A. Hayek, *New Studies in Philosophy, Politics, Economics, and the History of Ideas* (Routledge 1978); for further elaboration, see the first chapter of Christina Petsoulas, *Hayek's Liberalism and Its Origins: His Idea of Spontaneous Order and the Scottish Enlightenment* (Routledge 2013); Grahame Thompson, Jennifer Frances, Rosalind Levacic, Jeremy Mitchell, *Markets, Hierarchies and Networks: The Coordination of Social Life* (Sage Publications 1991).

⁴⁰ Frankel et al (ibid) 157; James G. March, 'The Business Firm as a Political Coalition' (1962) 24(4) *The Journal of Politics* 662; Neil Fligstein, 'Markets as Politics: A Political-Cultural Approach to Market Institutions' (1996) 61(4) *American Sociological Review*, 663, footnote 8; Neil Fligstein, *The Architecture of Markets: An Economic Sociology of Twenty-First-Century Capitalist Societies* (Princeton University Press 2002).

⁴¹ Michel Callon (ed.) *The Laws of the Markets* (Blackwell 1998) 4-8.

⁴² And thus of the corresponding goals of competition policy.

⁴³ This article by no means wants to argue that all public concerns will or should be approached through a market lens. The market cannot solve everything. That is exactly why the distinction is made below between specific public interests and the common good/collective protected by competition law.

good functioning, then laws meant to safeguard competition in markets are in essence about safeguarding the collective, rather than individual interest. Competition law is a form of public interest law,⁴⁴ at least in the sense that it ensures the conditions (of competition) in which the collective interest can be satisfied.⁴⁵

Despite normative disagreements between authors like Gerber and Posner, they fundamentally start from the similar premise that competition policy is justified by a collective societal good.

Positioning competition law in this manner embraces the view that competition law will promote the market as an 'institution', addressing the problems which keep it from functioning optimally. Benefits to individuals which emerge from the attempts to foster an ideal market are welcome and aspirational, but they are not the primary focus of the law in action. In other words, this view endorses the '*Institutionsschutztheorie*' rather than the '*Individualschutztheorie*'.⁴⁶ Individual competitors, who were harmed by the actions of a dominant undertaking, may hypothetically have a claim under competition law as well as under unfair competition rules or tort laws. Yet, if it is the competition authority who is to take action against this conduct, under competition law, it does not do so because it seeks to protect the individual competitors for their own sake, but because their continued survival in an industry acts as a 'buffer' against the erosion of remaining competition or 'the emergence of an absolute monopoly' to the detriment of the public.⁴⁷

⁴⁴ Niamh Dunne, 'Public Interest and EU Competition Law' (2020) 65(2) Antitrust Bulletin 256.

⁴⁵ This article tries to avoid the use of 'public interest' where possible. The 'public interest' is an ideal with no general meaning, the content of which varies depending on the policy. (See Bozeman (n 38 above) 87). In competition law discourse, however, it is customarily used not as a description of the goals of competition law, but rather as external aims which go beyond or are to be contrasted to the economic common good competition achieves. Competition policy pursues common goods (which can vary over time, e.g. debate about consumer welfare as an objective) which can be distinct from other common goods (i.e. racial inequity) which may require a consideration of how to reconcile competition's effects with other policy objectives. (See, for an example, Dunne's discussion of public interest goals which are distinct from the 'conventional (if disputed)' focus on efficiency: Dunne (n 44 above) 257-258. See also: David Reader, 'Accommodating Public Interest Considerations in Domestic Merger Control: Empirical Insights' (2016) CCP Working Paper 16-3; Giorgio Monti, 'Article 81 EC and Public Policy' (2002) 39 Common Market Law Review 1091.)

⁴⁶ Ioannis Lianos, 'Some reflections on the goals of EU competition law' in Ioannis Lianos and Damien Geradin (eds), *Handbook on European Competition Law: Substantive Aspects* (2013 Edward Elgar) 33.

⁴⁷ Wording from B Ong, 'Competition law and the common law of unfair competition' (PhD thesis, University of Oxford 2011) 135.

B. The collective interest in competition law

We find support for this view in both statute and case law in the EU.⁴⁸ Regulation 1/2003⁴⁹ provides support for this focus on collective rather than individual interests, by providing a meaningful (if broad) definition of the goal of competition law – ‘protecting competition *on the market*’ – and by contrasting it with laws with ‘other objectives’, such as fair trading rules, which the Regulation says apply ‘irrespective of the ... effects ... on competition on the market’.⁵⁰ The jurisprudence of the CJEU also emphasises the collective interest role of competition law. In *T-Mobile Netherlands* and at least 10 other cases, the Courts appear to acknowledge competition law’s dual nature of individual and collective interests, holding that the competition rules of the Treaty are ‘designed to protect not only the immediate interests of individual competitors or consumers, but also to protect the structure of the market and thus competition as such’.⁵¹ Advocate General Kokott added that this ‘competition as such’ refers to ‘competition as an institution’, and that competition law contributes to the ‘indirect protection’ of consumers.⁵² The Court of Justice has repeatedly held that the function of the competition rules is to prevent competition from being distorted to the detriment of the public interest, individual undertakings

⁴⁸ As well as in the US: ‘market definition furthers antitrust policy: the protection of competitive processes and not individual competitors’ (*Oltz v. St. Peter's Community Hospital* 861 F.2d 1440 (9th Cir. 1988), relying on *Gough*, 585 F.2d at 386); ‘As it has often been stated, “the antitrust laws * * * were enacted for “the protection of competition, not competitors * * *.”’ *Brunswick Corp. v. Pueblo Bowl-O-Mat, Inc.*, 429 U.S. 477, 488, 97 S.Ct. 690, 697 (1977). The conduct must have an adverse impact on the competitive conditions in general as they exist within the field of commerce in which the plaintiff is engaged.’ (*Gough v. Rossmoor Corp.* 585 F.2d 381 (9th Cir. 1978) 386).

⁴⁹ The distinction between rules which are about collective harm, such as to the ‘market’, and rules which are concerned with harm to individual interests, can also be illustrated at Member State level: in France, for example, abuse of economic dependence rules require that harm to competition on the market be shown, as well as an importance in an individual contractual relationship. French Cour de Cassation in: *Chavanoz* (2014)12-26705; *Societe CPS / Nina-Ricci et Paco-Rabanne* (2016) 14-25718; *Opera*, para 68, <https://www.autoritedelaconurrence.fr/sites/default/files/commitments//03d11.pdf>.

⁵⁰ Council Regulation (EC) No 1/2003 of 16 December 2002 on the implementation of the rules on competition laid down in Articles 81 and 82 of the Treaty, Recital 9 (own emphasis).

⁵¹ Case C-8/08 *T-Mobile Netherlands BV and Others* ECLI:EU:C:2009:343 para. 38; Case T-587/08 *Fresh Del Monte Produce, Inc. v European Commission* ECLI:EU:T:2013:129 para 460; Case T-588/08 *Dole Food Company, Inc. and Dole Germany OHG v European Commission* ECLI:EU:T:2013:130 para 65; T-386/10 *Dornbracht v Commission* ECLI:EU:T:2013:450 para 176; T-655/11 *FSL Holdings and Others v European Commission* ECLI:EU:T:2015:383 para 328; C-286/13 P *Dole Food Company, Inc. and Dole Fresh Fruit Europe v European Commission* ECLI:EU:C:2015:184 para 125; T-216/13 *Telefónica v Commission* ECLI:EU:T:2016:369 para 270; Case T-712/14 *Confédération européenne des associations d'horlogers-réparateurs (CEAHR) v European Commission* ECLI:EU:T:2017:748 para 112; Case T-180/15 *Icap plc and Others v European Commission* ECLI:EU:T:2017:795 para 55; Case T-105/17 *HSBC Holdings and Others v Commission* ECLI:EU:T:2019:675 para 65; Case T-799/17 *Scania AB and Others v European Commission* ECLI:EU:T:2022:48 para 321; Case C-883/19 P *HSBC Holdings and Others v Commission* ECLI:EU:C:2023:11 para 121.

⁵² Advocate General Kokott’s Opinion in Case C-8/08 *T-Mobile Netherlands BV and Others* ECLI:EU:C:2009:110 para 58 (which refers to ‘competition as such’ (as an institution)).

and consumers.⁵³ Moreover, Advocate General Kokott reflects clearly in her *British Airways* Opinion that, under Article 102 TFEU, conduct is not abusive ‘only once it has concrete effects on individual/market participants’,⁵⁴ but ‘as soon as’ the purpose of protecting competition from distortion and safeguarding a state of effective competition is prejudiced.⁵⁵ Her words support the idea that competition law protects the collective interest in competition on the market first and foremost, with benefits to individual market participants (be they competitors or customers) as welcomed but ancillary benefits (and not necessarily proven in every case). Although other Advocate Generals have been less explicit than AG Kokott, their Opinions also reveal the dual nature of competition law enforcement. Advocate General Jacobs, in *Bronner*, contrasts ‘the primary purpose’ of ‘the prevention of the distortion of competition’ (which itself safeguards the interest of consumers) with the protection of the position of particular competitors.⁵⁶ Advocate General Sagio stated in *Eco Swiss* that ‘the competition rules in question, while they govern the conduct of individuals, also pursue objectives of a general nature such as the smooth functioning of the common market and the well-being of consumers.’ They added that ‘the supervisory action of the Commission [is] intended precisely to ensure that individuals do not pursue their activities in such a manner as to prevent those public interest objectives from being achieved.’⁵⁷ The Opinions of AG Wahl could be read more sceptically, since they put more emphasis on the direct

⁵³ Case 136/79 National Panasonic (UK) Limited v Commission of the European Communities ECLI:EU:C:1980:169 paras 4 and 20; Joined Cases 46/87 and 227/88 Hoechst AG v Commission of the European Communities ECLI:EU:C:1989:337 para 25; Joined cases 97/87, 98/87 and 99/87 Dow Chemical Ibérica, SA, and others v Commission of the European Communities ECLI:EU:C:1989:380 para 22; Case 374/87 Orkem v Commission of the European Communities ECLI:EU:C:1989:387 para 19; Case T-65/99 Strintzis Lines Shipping SA v Commission of the European Communities ECLI:EU:T:2003:336 para 40; Case T-66/99 Minoan Lines SA v Commission of the European Communities ECLI:EU:T:2003:337 para 50; Case C-94/00 Roquette Frères SA v Directeur général de la concurrence, de la consommation et de la répression des fraudes, and Commission of the European Communities ECLI:EU:C:2002:603 para 42; Case C-52/09 TeliaSonera Sverige ECLI:EU:C:2011:83 para. 22; Case C-377/20 Servizio Elettrico Nazionale SpA and Others v Autorità Garante della Concorrenza e del Mercato and Others ECLI:EU:C:2022:379 para 41; Case T-621/16 České dráhy v Commission ECLI:EU:T:2018:367 para 150, not published but cited in Case T-452/20 Meta Platforms Ireland Ltd v Commission ECLI:EU:T:2023:277 para 149.

⁵⁴ Opinion of Advocate General Kokott in Case C-95/04 P British Airways plc v Commission of the European Communities ECLI:EU:C:2006:133 para 69 (own emphasis).

⁵⁵ Opinion of Advocate General Kokott in Case C-95/04 P British Airways plc v Commission of the European Communities ECLI:EU:C:2006:133 paras 69 and 86.

⁵⁶ Case C-7/97 Oscar Bronner GmbH & Co. KG v Mediaprint Zeitungs- und Zeitschriftenverlag GmbH & Co. KG, Mediaprint Zeitungsvertriebsgesellschaft mbH & Co. KG and Mediaprint Anzeigengesellschaft mbH & Co. KG. ECLI:EU:C:1998:264 para 58. Note that the exact interpretation of this statement was subject to debate in *British Airways*, see AG Kokott’s opinion footnote 87. Moreover, AG Bronner’s statement has been interpreted as a requirement of consumer harm in addition to harm to competition as such, which is a question outside the scope of this article (see, for example, Opinion of Advocate General Mazák in Case C-202/07 P France Télécom SA v Commission of the European Communities ECLI:EU:C:2008:520 para 74, as well as Opinion in Case C-52/09 Konkurrensverket v TeliaSonera Sverige AB ECLI:EU:C:2010:483 para 30 and the Opinion of Advocate General Rantos in Case C-42/21 P Lietuvos geležinkeliai v Commission ECLI:EU:C:2022:537 para 65).

⁵⁷ Case C-126/97 Eco Swiss China Time v Benetton International NV ECLI:EU:C:1999:97 para 42.

effects of conduct⁵⁸ including on individual competitors, without explicitly considering the dual nature in the same manner as Advocate General Kokott. However, we would argue this is too restrictive a reading, one which contradicts the more general references to free competition and to the 'loss to society'⁵⁹ which flows from these harms, as well as the reiteration that competition law 'protects competition, not competitors'. AG Wahl is well-known for their references to consumer well-being, but not only should this be read as a reference to consumers as a group not as individuals,⁶⁰ but in *MEO* the Advocate General stated that the conduct has to 'restrict competition *and* diminish the well-being of consumers',⁶¹ indicating a dual requirement. The impact of a practice on a specific trading partner is not sufficient to identify a distortion of competition.⁶²

The Court of Justice has emphasised this dual nature, as a reaction to the in its view erroneous emphasis by the Court of First Instance on final consumers, by holding that competition law '... aims to protect not only the interests of competitors or of consumers, but also the structure of the market and, in so doing, competition as such.'⁶³

Moreover, even private enforcement sheds light on this dual nature, as the development of the doctrine on private enforcement of competition law indicates that even private claims contribute to a dual objective of protecting the public interest and private interests. The

⁵⁸ E.g. opinions in case C-194/14 P, *AC-Treuhand AG v Commission* ECLI:EU:C:2015:350, Case C-177/16, *Biedrība 'Autortiesību un komunikācijas konsultāciju aģentūra – Latvijas Autoru apvienība' v Konkurences padome*, Opinion of AG Wahl, ECLI:EU:C:2017:286

⁵⁹ Case C-724/17, *Vantaan kaupunki v Skanska Industrial Solutions Oy and Others*, ECLI:EU:C:2019:100 para 50.

⁶⁰ E.g. Case C-194/14 P, *AC-Treuhand AG v Commission* ECLI:EU:C:2015:350 para 1 and 45. See also the argument that 'consumer well-being' is a mistranslation of consumer welfare in Assimakis Komninos, 'Consumer Welfare' and the EU Courts: An Unexpected Refuge for a Persecuted Concept?' in Oles Andriychuk, (ed.) *Antitrust and the Bounds of Power – 25 Years On* (Bloomsbury Publishing 2023) 78.

⁶¹ Case C-525/16, *MEO – Serviços de Comunicações e Multimédia SA v Autoridade da Concorrência*, ECLI:EU:C:2017:1020 para 64.

⁶² *Ibid.* para 98. The particular case concerned a discriminatory practice, a type of abuse where there had been debate prior to *MEO*, given the lack of clarity on the need to show a distortion of competition in the case of a 'competitive disadvantage'. In *MEO*, AG Wahl made it explicit that actual or potential anticompetitive effects are indeed necessary (para 63), which the Court (perhaps more cautiously) seemed to confirm (EU:C:2018:270). See Brenda Sufrin, Niamh Dunne, and Alison Jones, *Jones and Sufrin's Competition Law* (8th edn., Oxford University Press, 2023) 580; Cyril Ritter, 'Price Discrimination as an Abuse of a Dominant Position under Article 102 TFEU: *MEO*' (2019) 56 *Common Market Law Review* 259.

⁶³ *Joined Cases C-501/06 P, C-513/06 P, C-515/06 P and C-519/06 P, GlaxoSmithKline Services Unlimited v Commission, Commission v GlaxoSmithKline Services Unlimited, European Association of Euro Pharmaceutical Companies (EAEPC) v Commission and Asociación de exportadores españoles de productos farmacéuticos (Aseprofar) v Commission*, ECLI:EU:C:2009:610 para 63.

Damages Directive⁶⁴ considers that Articles 101 and 102 of the TFEU are ‘a matter of public policy’,⁶⁵ infringements of which *also* generate a right to compensation for harm to individuals.⁶⁶

The interest of individuals in compensation shares a rationale with the interest they have in a declaration by the Commission that an infringement of competition law has indeed taken place. References to the interests of individuals should not be read as the only or even primary interest in protecting competition law, even though they appear in the case law.

The debate before the adoption of the Damages Directive centred on whether private enforcement was intended primarily to enable the effective protection of individuals (with compensation as principal aim) or to provide for effective enforcement of competition law (contributing to the aim of deterrence, alongside public enforcement).⁶⁷ Ultimately, the Damages Directive relied on both the compensation and deterrence objectives, with actions for damages contributing to discouraging practices which may restrict competition.⁶⁸ For our purposes, the important question is not whether it is compensation or deterrence which provides support for the development of private enforcement, but rather whether the compensation – or harm to individual interests – is separate and independent of the need to show harm to collective interest. This article argues it is not, and that this supports the case that the market – and thus market definition – plays a central role in enforcement.

Civil actions for damages are, in the words of AG Pitruzzella, actions brought ‘in order to obtain recognition of legal consequences in relations between private individuals arising from an infringement of competition rules – in particular, compensation for harm suffered as a result of such an infringement.’⁶⁹ To bring a claim a claimant has to start by proving a competition law infringement.⁷⁰ This involves showing, in addition to either some form of cooperation between

⁶⁴ Directive 2014/104/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 November 2014 on certain rules governing actions for damages under national law for infringements of the competition law provisions of the Member States and of the European Union, OJ L 349, 5.12.2014 [‘Damages Directive’].

⁶⁵ *Ibid.*, Recital 1.

⁶⁶ *Ibid.*, Recital 2.

⁶⁷ See Sufrin, Dunne and Jones (n 62 above) 1039, citing *Nebbia*, Nazzini. See also ICN Development of Private Enforcement of Competition Law in ICN Jurisdictions Subgroup 2 of the Cartel Working Group, comparing the EU system’s modern focus on compensation to the US system’s consideration of deterrence.

⁶⁸ Case C-25/21, *ZA and Others v Repsol Comercial de Productos Petrolíferos*, ECLI:EU:C:2023:298, para 52.

⁶⁹ Case C-25/21 *Repsol Comercial de Productos Petrolíferos* ECLI:EU:C:2022:659 para 35.

⁷⁰ Case C-267/20 *Volvo DAF Trucks NV* ECLI:EU:C:2022:494 para 60; Case C-25/21 *Opinion of AG* ECLI:EU:C:2022:659 para 61: ‘The existence of an infringement of competition rules which has allegedly caused the damage for which compensation is sought in the action for damages is among the necessary elements which the injured party must have in order to bring an action for damages.’; Case C-25/21 ECLI:EU:C:2023:298 para 39: ‘Since, as is apparent from the case-law of the Court, the existence of an infringement of competition law, the existence of harm caused by that infringement, the causal link

undertakings or a dominant position, that competition on the market has been distorted. Establishing an infringement of competition law requires articulating a theory of harm, in which it can be shown that conduct is restrictive of competition and that the market would have been different absent the conduct.⁷¹ In follow-on cases, this will have been established in a previous decision, but in stand-alone claims (that is, claims which does not follow on from an administrative decision of infringement by an authority), the claimant will have to provide such evidence themselves. It can be argued that the first step – showing a competition law infringement – is a matter of showing how the collective interest is affected; while the second step – showing that the claimant suffered damage from the infringement – focuses on individual interests. This is best illustrated by stand-alone civil actions, although there are very few, since in these cases the two steps are assessed as distinct and consecutive. The UK’s Competition Appeal Tribunal articulated this well in its *Sainsbury’s* judgment: ‘the question of whether it is impossible to carry on a primary operation or activity without a particular term, is very different from the question of whether that term is restrictive of competition, which invokes an inquiry as to the nature of competition in the relevant market absent the restriction in question.’⁷²

It is clear that both the law on public enforcement and private enforcement supports the view that competition law enforcement pursues the collective interest first, with possibilities for the protection of individual interests following on from this aim. This is the case generally, without the need for clarity on the exact goals of competition law. We can leaving aside for now the question of what competition is, and what the goals should be of competition law enforcement. Regardless of whether one is concerned with impediments to the ‘market mechanism’ or (narrower) focuses on welfare, harm to individuals is outside the scope of the analysis in a competition law case, unless this individual harm is part of or the result of harm to competition.⁷³ This article argues that harm to individual interests is separate and independent of the need to show harm to collective interest, and that this supports the case that the market plays a central role in enforcement.

between that harm and the said infringement, and the identity of the perpetrator of that same infringement are among the necessary elements which the injured party must have in order to bring an action for damages.’

⁷¹ CAT Sainsburys judgment (1241/5/7/15 (T) Sainsbury’s Supermarkets Ltd v MasterCard Incorporated and Others 2016] CAT 11), in which the infringement of Article 101 TFEU/Chapter I of the Competition Act 1998 is established first by showing the conduct appreciably restricts competition, before damages can be awarded for breach of statutory duty, and in particular paras 105, 420–421. In France: Tribunal de commerce de Paris, 31 janvier 2012 T. com. Paris, 31 janv. 2012 Bottin Cartographes c/ Google ; T. com. Paris, 23 sept. 2019, n° 2019000381 Schneider Electric France.

⁷² CAT Sainsburys judgment (1241/5/7/15) para 116.

⁷³ See, in this regard, Supreme Court in a US case: National Soc’y of Prof. Engineers v. United States, 435 U.S. 679, 696 (1978)).

Callon explained, in his studies on economic life, the necessity of delineating market boundaries: framing this network of relationships between different actors, allows one to define actors and goods as independent of each other as well as in their character as being a component of the whole. It enables us to describe them and this network, and consider the effects of actions upon them and the network.⁷⁴ The exercise of market definition in competition law is such a framing, within the context of the law, enabling the enforcer to identify those actors and relations who may be affected by the conduct of one (or more) actors. It enables the authority to identify the network as a whole of constituent parts, in order to determine whether there is harm which affects the network rather than just an isolated part.

There is a wide variety of market notions in economic and legal literature, although they share some common concepts.⁷⁵ Markets have to be understood within the context of the study, and can vary with it, as argued by this author elsewhere.⁷⁶ Thus, there will inevitably need to be clarity on the goals pursued by the law and in each investigation, to assess the validity of the market definition exercise. We can, undoubtedly, have a debate about the content and scope of the collective interest, particularly whether the collective interest amounts to the aggregation of private interests or a common mutual concern distinct from private interests, or both.⁷⁷ This article refrains from addressing this debate at present. It is important to acknowledge that this debate needs to be had for the purpose of setting the scope of competition law and the boundaries on its use to intervene in economic activity.⁷⁸ However, this discussion – though fundamental – goes beyond the current scope of this paper. This paper’s main aim, for now, is to put forward that the competition authority illustrates with its market definition exercise how its intervention would safeguard broader interests / group, rather than (a select few) individuals (interests).

⁷⁴ Callon (n 41 above) 17.

⁷⁵ Most notably: property and goods, buyers and sellers, money, and information. See Bruce G. Carruthers and Sarah L. Babb, *Economy/Society: Markets, Meanings, and Social Structure* (Sage Publishing 2013) 4; Eckehard F. Rosenbaum, ‘What is a Market? On the Methodology of a Contested Concept’ (2000) 58(4) *Review of Social Economy* 455.

⁷⁶ Eben (n 8 above) 586.

⁷⁷ See, for example, Mazzucato’s critical description of the ‘good’ in economic theory as ‘an aggregated form of private interest’, and her proposition to consider the common good which is ‘not merely about maximising the sum of aggregate individual interests; but about common interests and mutual concern’ (Mariana Mazzucato, ‘Governing the Economics of the Common Good: From Correcting Market Failures to Shaping Collective Goals’ (2024) 27(1) *Journal of Economic Policy Reform* 1 and 3.

⁷⁸ This author does not, in fact, consider that the collective interest for competition law purposes should encompass public policy goals best addressed through non-market intervention.

IV. Market definition on a scale: competition law and other legal fields

It could, perhaps, be argued that competition law enforcement can protect the collective and not (only) individual interests without relying on the 'market' concept. For instance, someone who argues that the objective of competition law is to achieve consumer welfare or overall static efficiency, may consider that it is enough to show the direct impact of conduct on welfare. However, even without wading into the debate on the exact ultimate benefit competition policy is meant to achieve, this approach does not explain the choice for competition law over other policies which may also pursue welfare or efficiency. Despite some calls that competition law should not apply where other regulatory intervention is better able to achieve the benefit intended, competition law can be and has been used even where other policies may in theory be more appropriate or where there is a regulatory gap.⁷⁹ It is the contention of this article that the distinction between competition law and other laws and policies lies in the explicit reference to an embodiment of the collective interest – the market.

Certainly, competition law is not the only area of law or policy which justifies its adoption or enforcement by reference to the market. There are various degrees to which the market is used as a legitimising force for policy or laws. On one end of the scale, there is the rhetorical usage of the 'market' in political discourse,⁸⁰ where the concept is used to legitimise political decisions (be they legislative or not) without the intention to assess the workings of or impact on the market in concreto. Evidently, this rhetorical usage is possible without clarifying the boundaries of this market. In the middle of the scale are those laws and regulations whose adoption has been justified, in abstract terms, by the need to protect market mechanisms and a market ordering, but whose application and enforcement remains focused on individual interests or harms. At the end of the scale are those laws and policies which are, in their application and enforcement, directly intended to remedy harm *to the market*.

Let us first reflect on those laws, in the middle of the scale, whose adoption may be justified by reference to the market, but whose enforcement is focused on the harm to individual interests.

A. Laws protecting individual interests

The previous section argued that harm to individuals on its own is outside the scope of competition law, unless it is part of or the result of harm to the competitive market more broadly.⁸¹ This distinguishes competition law from other areas of law – such as unfair trading

⁷⁹ Monti (n 12 above) 60.

⁸⁰ Matthew Watson, *The Market* (Agenda publishing 2018) 1.

⁸¹ See, in this regard, Supreme Court in a US case: *National Soc'y of Prof. Engineers v. United States*, 435 U.S. 679, 696 (1978)).

practices,⁸² consumer protection law, tort law, and others⁸³ – which focus on harm to individual consumers or individual undertakings.⁸⁴ These other areas of law do not require market definition as a matter of legitimacy.

There are other areas of law in whose application authorities or courts may refer to ‘markets’ (perhaps even defining these by reference to demand substitution), and yet these markets are not defined with the same regularity and systematism, nor are they considered necessities, in the same way as they are in competition law. Intellectual property law is a prime example of such a field of law, since the market may be ‘defined’ in copyright cases or trademark cases, not to determine harm to a collective, but in order to determine the range over which rivalry occurs, particularly identifying the right holders and their rivals with particular emphasis on those infringing their rights.⁸⁵ This should not be surprising, if considered from the perspective of the objectives of enforcing intellectual property law, compared to competition law: though intellectual property law may have been adopted with the goals of long-term collective interests (in innovation, production for the good of society as a whole), its direct scope is the individual interests of right holders. It is not imperative to define the boundaries of a ‘market’, including all those actors and activities within a competitive relationship, to legitimately determine whether a specific right holder’s interests have been affected. As Hovenkamp notes, in intellectual property cases, ‘harm to the market’ may mean ‘harm to the plaintiff’, but this cannot be the case in competition law cases.⁸⁶

⁸² See Regulation 1/2003, Recital 9, which contrast competition law’s goal of ‘protecting competition on the market’ with laws with ‘other objectives’, such as fair trading rules which apply ‘irrespective of the ... effects ... on competition on the market’. See also Or Brook and Magali Eben, ‘Article 3 of Regulation 1/2003: a historical and empirical account of an unworkable compromise’ (2024) 12(1) *Journal of Antitrust Enforcement* 45.

⁸³ This article does not reflect on criminal rules such as commercial bribery or financial regulation, where the protection of market in the collective interest may play an important role. Farmer, for example, argues for seeing the market as an ‘interest’ to be protected (Lindsay Farmer, ‘The ‘Market’ in Criminal Law Theory’ (2022) 85 *The Modern Law Review* 439). The logic here is the same, but this article adds a degree of separation, in that it sees the market as a representation of the collective, who is protection is therefore in the common interest. There is scope for future work to develop reflections on the need for market definition, comparing competition law with such fields of law.

⁸⁴ Such as consumer protection or privacy laws, see Maureen K. Ohlhausen and Ben Rossen, ‘Privacy and Competition: Discord or Harmony?’ (2022) 67 *The Antitrust Bulletin* 558.

⁸⁵ Herbet Hovenkamp, ‘Markets in IP and Antitrust’ (2012) 100 *The Georgetown Law Journal* 2134 and 2137. Note that the purposes and approaches to markets vary across the different areas of intellectual property. See, e.g. Anna Kingsbury, ‘Market Definition in Intellectual Property Law: Should Intellectual Property Courts Use an Antitrust Approach to Market Definition?’ (2004) 1 *Marquette Intellectual Property Law Review* 63

⁸⁶ Hovenkamp, *ibid.* 2149; Christina Bohannon and Herbert Hovenkamp, *Creation Without Restraint: Promoting Liberty and Rivalry in Innovation* (Oxford University Press 2012) 48.

Indeed, a historical analysis of the 'market' concept in US copyright law⁸⁷ reveals that it was introduced precisely to determine when the commercial interests of a copyright holder were harmed,⁸⁸ thus justifying a finding of infringement. To balance the interests of individual rightsholders against the public interest, the market (and 'substitution') serves as a benchmark for harm to the individual, rather than as benchmark for collective interests.

Under US copyright law, the 'fair use' doctrine sets out conditions under which anyone can use copyrighted material without permission from the rightsholders. When assessing whether the use falls within the fair use exception, the courts can refer to the 'potential market' for the copyrighted work and the 'market harm' which would occur if use of it was possible for others than the copyright holder. Although this wording may sound similar to that articulated above for competition law, in reality market harm is just another way of phrasing harm to the copyright holder. The courts may consider substitution or the 'market' for the work in order to determine whether a copy by another would reduce the opportunities of the copyright holder to commercial exploit the work (or, in the words of Stadler, reduce 'the ability of a copyright owner to earn a profit').⁸⁹ If the use of a work fulfils the demand for the original - 'substitutes' for it - then it can be blocked in favour of the copyright holder.⁹⁰ This is not to say that there is no public interest involved in this assessment:⁹¹ the fair use doctrine is a balancing act between the interests of original creators (copyright holders) and other members of the public, designed to ensure that there are proper incentives to create. Thus, by engaging in a market definition under fair use, the courts fulfil the underlying assumption of that law that harming an individual's commercial opportunities will lead to a less optimal societal outcome, without having to identify actual collective harm in cases.

Trade mark law is another area of law where the 'market' could conceivably play a role in enforcement. It poses a particular quandary, however, given the apparent tension between the collective interest aims of the law and the individual rights focus in most of its enforcement. Not only are the objectives of trade mark law the subject of some debate (a situation not unfamiliar

⁸⁷ Isabella Alexander, *Copyright Law and the Public Interest in the Nineteenth Century* (Bloomsbury Publishing 2010) 185-186.

⁸⁸ Commercial interests which were, at least since 19th century in US law, identified in terms of the market value of an intellectual work to the copyright holder (see Alexander, *ibid.* 155, footnote 88, which in turn cites Oren Bracha, 'The Ideology of Authorship Revisited: Authors, Markets, and Liberal Values in Early American Copyright' (2009) 118 *Yale Law Journal* 186.)

⁸⁹ Sara K. Stadler, 'Relevant markets for copyrighted works' (2009) 34(4) *Journal of Corporation Law* 1066.

⁹⁰ *Ibid.* 1059.

⁹¹ The fair use doctrine is in the public interest. In the words of Anderson et al, '[w]hen enforcement of copyrights would not advance the constitutional goals behind the law, a fair use defense will be successful.' (Michael Anderson, Paul F. Brown, and Andrew P. Cores, 'Market Substitution and Copyrights: Predicting Fair Use Case Law' (1993) 10(33) *University of Miami Entertainment & Sports Law Review* 39).

to competition lawyers), but it is also rather unclear whether its primary aim is the individual or the collective. Although the protection of consumers of competing products seems to be an ultimate goal, the actual rights given and injury addressed appears to focus primarily on the individual producer – with any benefits to the ‘market’ assumed to follow naturally. The granting and protection of trade marks has multiple objectives, two of the most prominent being the avoidance of consumer confusion (and reduction of their search costs) and the protection of the reputation of the (proprietor of the) products trademarked.⁹²

The classifications of products within specific categories (Nice classes) is a part of the registration of a trade mark,⁹³ but the categorisation of products also plays a role in the subsequent enforcement of a registered trade mark. There are several situations in which it can be said that a sign infringes a trade mark, most of which involve some consideration of the similarity between the goods or services (the ‘products’) of the owner of the trade mark and the alleged infringer. It will be necessary, depending on the circumstances, to establish either that the products of the parties (claimant and defendant) are identical or that they are similar and there is a likelihood of confusion.⁹⁴ The Court of Justice has referred to the products’ nature, end-users, intended purpose and method of use as factors for the similarity of goods and services.⁹⁵ This exercise appears reminiscent of the qualitative substitution exercises in antitrust market definition, where similarity between products is considered as a factor. The Court also referred to the ‘competition’ between products as a relevant factor.⁹⁶ Yet, despite this prima facie kinship, the trade mark exercise does not amount to a full market definition exercise, since it focuses only on the products of the parties without expanding the analysis to other (third party) products.⁹⁷

⁹² Lionel Bently, Brad Sherman, Dev Gangjee, and Philip Johnson, *Intellectual Property Law* (Oxford University Press, 6th edition, 2022) 857-861; Kingsbury (n 85 above) 66.

⁹³ ‘Goods and services in respect of which trade mark registration is applied for shall be classified in conformity with the system of classification established by the Nice Agreement Concerning the International Classification of Goods and Services for the Purposes of the Registration of Marks of 15 June 1957 (‘the Nice Classification’), as stipulated in Article 33(1) of Regulation (EU) 2017/1001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 June 2017 on the European Union trade mark.

⁹⁴ See Section 10 of Trade Marks Act 1994 (UK); Article 9 of Regulation (EU) 2017/1001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 June 2017 on the European Union trade mark;

⁹⁵ Case C-39/97 Canon Kabushiki Kaisha and Metro-Goldwyn-Mayer Inc., formerly Pathé Communications Corporation, para 24; Case T-169/03 Sergio Rossi SpA v OHIM ECLI:EU:T:2005:72, para 54.

⁹⁶ *Ibid.*

⁹⁷ Kingsbury ((n 85 above) 74) suggested that ‘antitrust market definition could usefully be imported into trademark infringement’ in the US. Her analysis does not, however, consider whether there are distinct requirements of harm/injury in antitrust law and trademark law in the US and the relationship with the market definition exercise. Her argument is, in essence, a plea for more empirical evidence in the enforcement of trademark law. Another scholar, Porangaba, suggests that in the EU there is scope for ‘a more realistic (or hybrid) construction of the average consumer’ and an ‘infringement assessment ...

Whether a use infringes depends on whether the use affects the trade mark's functions, particularly its 'essential function of guaranteeing to consumers the origin of the goods'.⁹⁸ Thus, infringing use is that which jeopardises the function of the trade mark- and thus creates harm to consumers - in relation to a specific product (that of the claimant). Insofar they reduce consumer confusion and search costs, trade marks can be said to operate in the public interest, by creating the informational conditions for the proper functioning of the market.⁹⁹ However, the process of establishing an infringement seems to be less concerned with establishing harm to the collective (as represented by the 'market' in some form) than with the proprietor's rights associated with a specific trade mark.

This focus on the specific parties remains evident when considering that the consumers whose confusion seems to matter when considering a conflict between an applicant's mark and an earlier mark. Bently et al explain that a question can sometimes arise as to whether 'it is the opponent's public that must be confused, or the applicant's public?'¹⁰⁰ The answer by the General Court has been that the relevant public is the consumers who are likely to use the products of both parties¹⁰¹ - it did not mention the consumers for all substitutable products, but focused its answer on the parties to the case.

Although similarity between products is an element of the overall showing of injury to the proprietor of the trade mark (by virtue of the confusion of consumers or reputational damage), there is no definition of a market (as a collective of products and economic actors) as a proxy for harm to that collective.

Lemley and McKenna argue that (US) trade mark law has no theory of injury that 'distinguishes harm to legitimate interests the law should protect from a mere desire to capture a benefit enjoyed by another' company. They put forward that a legal claim that a defendant is unjustly benefitting by using a plaintiff's mark 'should be (but is not) accompanied by a theory of why that benefit should rightly belong to the plaintiff'¹⁰² which has a relationship with the harm to consumers in the market more broadly. According to them, the current approach rests on a belief that trade mark owners 'ought to own whatever value the ... mark has' and have a right to enter the provision of other products, even in the absence of injury to consumers. They critique

infused with market realities.' (Luis Porangaba, 'A Contextual Account of the Trade Mark Functions Theory' (2018) *Intellectual Property Quarterly* 251)

⁹⁸ Arsenal v. Reed, Case C-206/01 [2002] ECR I-10273, [51]; O2 (UK) v. Hutchison 3G UK, Case C-533/06 [2008] ECR I-4231, [57]. As cited in Bently et al (n 92 above) footnote 92, 1136.

⁹⁹ Bently et al (n 92 above) 860-861.

¹⁰⁰ Ibid. 1055-1056.

¹⁰¹ Case T-400/06 Zero Industry v. OHIM and zero Germany, , EU:T:2009:331, para 39.

¹⁰² Mark A. Lemley and Mark P. McKenna, 'Owning Mark(et)s' (2010) 09(2) Michigan Law Review 137.

the expansive interpretation courts have given to injury to the trade mark owner, emphasising that the needed rationale behind giving trademark owners such expansive rights, is that there is a risk of consumer harm where goods are 'so closely related that consumers will draw inferences about product quality from the use of the mark'.¹⁰³ Lemley and McKenna, in essence, argue for a broader conception of groups of products (potential 'markets') and urge more consideration of harm to a collective. However, as long as (the enforcement of) trade mark law considers injury to the individual trade mark owner first and foremost, without the need to show injury to the collective, a market definition exercise in the sense of this article is not needed.

B. Laws protecting the market

The market can be invoked as a legitimising force for policy or laws in various ways. Even where the law is said to be adopted to protect the market, the 'market' may not need to play a functional role in the enforcement. At one end, political discourse often employs the 'market' rhetorically to justify (legislative) decisions,¹⁰⁴ without the intention to consider the actual impact on the market when applying the law. Evidently, this rhetorical usage is possible without clarifying the boundaries of this market. This is clearly distinct from those laws and policies which are, in their application and enforcement, directly intended to remedy harm *to the market*.

The extent to which it is necessary to establish strict boundaries of a market will depend on the manner in which the 'market' is used as a rationale for the law. The market may be used a heuristic device,¹⁰⁵ an abstract model of the benefits which will emerge if certain behavioural and institutional conditions are satisfied, to justify the protection of those conditions. For example, a law may guarantee property rights or safeguard contract freedom, as pre-conditions for achieving the benefits of the ideal 'market' order. The protection of the market is, at most, indirect. There is no need, as such, to establish the exact boundaries of this market.

The situation is different, however, where the law aims to guarantee the functioning of the market itself, directly protecting the market as an interest in itself. Where this is the case, clarity is needed on what the market is. Where the rationale of the law is the protection of the market (in its 'normal' or rather expected functioning) rather than individual interests, then articulating the scope of the market is advisable.¹⁰⁶ Indeed, establishing the scope of the market will

¹⁰³ *Ibid.* 144-145.

¹⁰⁴ Watson (n 80 above) 1.

¹⁰⁵ Farmer (n 83 above) 442.

¹⁰⁶ See a related more abstract argument, in the different context of criminal law, in Farmer (n 83 above) 440.

legitimise the actions undertaken to enforce the law, since it will rely on its primary object to justify the actions taken.

Even in this context, however, one can nuance the necessity to define a market with specific boundaries. The difference lies in the extent of evidence required to establish an infringement of the law: boundaries of market need to be drawn rather precisely where, to establish a violation of the law, harm to the market *has to be shown*. The enforcement of the law depends on the definition of the market. It may be, however, that the evidentiary burden is reduced to presumptions of harm. This can be the cases in the case-by-case enforcement of a law such as competition law, for example in the context of 'by object' infringements.¹⁰⁷

The situation is different, however, where regulatory obligations or prohibitions have been established without the need to evidence harm, as a general rule rather than as an evidentiary short-cut. In the context of such regulations, the enforcer will not have to engage in a delineation of the market on a case-by-case basis. In that case, the onus of a proper definition of the market is not on the enforcer of the law, but rather on the legislator. After all, the legislator justifies the adoption of the law by reference to the harm to the market that certain conduct may cause. If the market the legislator uses as justification for the law does not have a clear meaning, there is no litmus test for effectiveness of the law.

C. The Digital Markets Act

It can be argued that the Digital Markets Act is exactly this type of law: one where the functioning of the 'market' is a legislative justification for the regulation, rather than an analytical unit of enforcement. Market definition does not play a formal role within the DMA, and yet it would be remiss not to point out the invisible role the market may play in the background.

In the lead up to the adoption of the Digital Markets Act (DMA)¹⁰⁸ in the EU, and the Digital Markets, Competition and Consumers (DMCC) Act in the UK, abandoning 'formal' market definition was a key topic of the discussion. The arguments for avoiding a market definition exercise in each enforcement action contained both a practical and a substantive element. In practical terms, it was considered that market definition was too cumbersome a requirement.¹⁰⁹ Not only were

¹⁰⁷ Magali Eben, 'Market definition' (Edward Elgar encyclopaedia of competition law, forthcoming).

¹⁰⁸ Regulation (EU) 2022/1925 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 September 2022 on contestable and fair markets in the digital sector and amending Directives (EU) 2019/1937 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Digital Markets Act), OJ L 265, 12.10.2022.

¹⁰⁹ Alexandre de Streel, Richard Feasey, Giorgio Monti, Jan Krämer and Martin Cave, 'Digital Markets Act: Making Economic Regulation of Platforms Fit for the Digital Age' (December 2020) Centre on Regulation Europe (CerRE) Report, 34, available at <https://cerre.eu/publications/digital-markets-act-economic-regulation-platforms-digital-age/>; UK Government (Department for Digital, Culture, Media & Sport and Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy), Consultation document: 'A New Pro-Competition

there clear methodological challenges to defining markets in the digital economy, but it was a lengthy process imposing a high evidentiary burden on the enforcers. In substantive terms, it was argued that the DMA would pursue objectives additional and distinct from those in competition law – such as ensuring fairness in the market – which may make a ‘relevant market’-based approach unsuited to the enforcement of the regulation.¹¹⁰ It could be argued, indeed, that at least its ‘fairness’ objective distinguishes the DMA from a type of law directly remedying harm to a market. Its ‘contestability’ objective may be more similar to competition law, though this is up for debate.¹¹¹ This section returns to the discussion.

What is clear is that the DMA adopts a ‘per se’ approach, different from the case-by-case approach of establishing harm which characterises competition law. The enforcement of competition law poses a constraint on authorities, by asking that they establish harmful effects before finding a breach and imposing remedies.¹¹² This is not the case in the Digital Markets Act, which bases its findings of infringements on breaches of per se prohibitions, without any need to establish that actual harm to competition occurred. As the General Court reiterated in *Bytedance*, the DMA is distinct from competition law since its objective is to ensure the desired character of markets – contestable and fair – but without considering ‘actual, potential or presumed effects of the conduct ... on competition on a given market.’¹¹³

The DMA may have been adopted with a view to attaining a desired market form, but at first glance harm does not play a role in the enforcement of the law. Harm of some sort to the market was – at most – presumed by the legislator when establishing which obligations and prohibitions would apply. The application of the DMA to companies does not require market definition to establish who or what is being harmed. The designation of gatekeepers does involve a step akin to the delineation of a ‘product’ in competition law – the CPS – but does not involve the further delineation of the competitive constraints relevant to the case.

Regime for Digital Markets’ (July 2021) para 54; DMA, *ibid.*, Recital 23 explicitly rules out the use of market definition to rebut the quantitative presumption for the designation of gatekeepers.

¹¹⁰ Jacques Crémer, Yves-Alexandre de Montjoye and Heike Schweitzer, Competition policy for the digital era, Final report for the European Commission (2019) 3, 46; Digital Markets Act Impact Assessment Study: Annexes 100-101, available at <https://op.europa.eu/s/zXqw>; UK Government, *ibid.*, para 54 and 72.

¹¹¹ Belle Beems, ‘The DMA in the Broader Regulatory Landscape of the EU: An Institutional Perspective’ (2023) 19 European Competition Journal 4; Friso Bostoën, ‘Understanding the Digital Markets Act’ (2023) 68 The Antitrust Bulletin 266; Pierre Larouche and Alexandre de Streel, ‘The European Digital Markets Act: A Revolution Grounded on Traditions’ (2021) 12 Journal of European Competition Law & Practice 544-545; Pablo Ibanez Colomo, ‘The Draft Digital Markets Act: A Legal and Institutional Analysis’ (2021) 12 Journal of European Competition Law & Practice 568.

¹¹² *Ibid.* 566.

¹¹³ Case T-1077/23, *Bytedance v Commission*, para 19; Digital Markets Act (n 108 above), Recital 11.

The process of designation and the appeals of the Commission's early designation decisions to the General Court did involve delineation exercises, particularly questions about the accurate delineation of the 'core platform services' (CPS)¹¹⁴ which shared some commonalities with 'focal product' delineations in the first stage of market definition in competition law cases. These delineations are crucial to identify the field of application of the DMA, but are seemingly unrelated to the interests the law protects.

As noted in Recital 15 of the DMA, the existence of a service qualifying as a CPS is not enough to fall within the scope of the regulation is the first step in establishing the applicability of the law. Once a CPS is identified, it has to be established that the CPS is an important gateway and is operated by an undertaking with a significant impact in the internal market and an entrenched and durable position.¹¹⁵ Article 2(2) lists 10 categories of CPS. A company may say its service does not at all constitute a CPS – and thus that none of the obligations and prohibitions apply to it. A company may also argue that a particular service is not a standalone CPS, but part of another CPS, which is a question akin to the standalone product question in tying cases.¹¹⁶ Thus, an obligation would apply to that service as part of another service, rather than separately.¹¹⁷ A different question is *which* category of CPS the service falls under. Some of the obligations and prohibitions of the DMA only apply to specific categories of CPS,¹¹⁸ so that the question of which category of CPS a service is, becomes essential not to determine whether the DMA applies but *how much* the DMA applies. The delineation exercise broadens or narrows the scope of application of the obligations.¹¹⁹

¹¹⁴ See Alba Ribera Martínez, 'The Requisite Legal Standard of the Digital Markets Act's Designation Process' (2024) *Journal of Competition Law & Economics*, advance access, <https://doi.org/10.1093/joclec/nhae011>, for an in-depth analysis of the European Commission's delineations of Core Platform Services and designation of gatekeepers.

¹¹⁵ Digital Markets Act (n 108 above), Recital 15.

¹¹⁶ See Magali Eben, 'Addressing the Main Hurdles of Product Market Definition for Online Services: Products, Price, and Dynamic Competition' (2019) PhD thesis, available at <http://etheses.whiterose.ac.uk/26343/>.

¹¹⁷ E.g. Meta – online social networking services, number-independent interpersonal communications services, online advertising services, OIS marketplace (Cases DMA.100020, 100024, 100035 and 100044) Decision of 5 September 2023; Alphabet – OIS verticals, OIS app stores, online search engines, video sharing, number-independent interpersonal communications services, operating systems, web browsers, online advertising services (Cases DMA.100011, 100002, 100004–100006, 100009, 100008 and 100010) Decision of 5 September 2023; Point also made in Bostoen and Monti 21, with extensive reference to Meta and Alphabet, see Friso Bostoen and Giorgio Monti, 'The Rhyme and Reason of Gatekeeper Designation under the Digital Markets Act' (SSRN working paper, 8 August 2024), available at https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4904116.

¹¹⁸ E.g. Digital Markets Act (n 108 above), Article 6(12) applies specifically to search engines and social networks.

¹¹⁹ A real-life example is the designation of TikTok, which was notified by ByteDance as a video-sharing service but was designated by the Commission as a social network. The Commission agreed that it met the characteristics of video-sharing, but considered that this was only one feature of the service. Social

These delineations of CPS are crucial to identify the field of application of the DMA, but not to determine whether harm occurred. They are seemingly unrelated to the interests the law protects. This is not where the delineation process ends, however. The steps after delineation of CPS are meant to determine whether the company offering the CPS is a gatekeeper. In these steps, the objectives of the law (and thus the interests meant to be safeguarded) – and particularly its contestability objective – could conceivably be relevant, since the DMA’s Recital 21 states that [a]n entrenched and durable position in its operations ... occurs notably where the contestability of the position of the undertaking providing the core platform service is limited.’ It was not unthinkable that the European Commission would bring a form of definition of the market back into its designation process, particularly when considering the contestability objective. Contestability is a distinct goal from effective competition, but does nonetheless overlap with it. In theory, a company may meet the quantitative thresholds for designation as a gatekeeper under the DMA,¹²⁰ and yet still be providing a counterweight as a challenger to other companies who are gatekeepers. As Bostoan and Monti note, designating such companies as gatekeepers – thus ensuring they have to comply with DMA obligations – may go against the DMA’s goal of contestability (by reducing their ability to challenge the existing gatekeepers), yet may still benefit its goal of fairness which may be achieved by (other) DMA obligations.¹²¹ A purposive approach to the designation of a gatekeeper would consider which objective(s) the law is meant to achieve and harm addressed when deciding whether or not to designate a company. However, the Commission and the General Court dismissed the consideration of this link between designation and the goals of the DMA as a matter of course. In *Bytedance*, the company had argued that its designation as a gatekeeper was ‘contrary to the DMA’s policy intent’, which the company interpreted as being to enable challengers to compete with well-established platforms.¹²² These arguments were dismissed as irrelevant by the Commission as well as the General Court.¹²³

Although the designation has an impact on whether – and to what extent – the law applies, it does not on the face of it play a role in establishing a theory of harm, since a theory of harm is not necessary in the first place to establish the applicability of an obligation or to impose a fine for

network was considered a better fit. See ByteDance – online social networking services (Case DMA.100040) Decision of 5 September 2023, paras 28–35.

¹²⁰ Offering a CPS and meeting the quantitative criteria of Article 3(2) for at least three years.

¹²¹ Friso Bostoan, F. and Giorgio Monti, ‘The Rhyme and Reason of Gatekeeper Designation under the Digital Markets Act’ (SSRN working paper, 8 August 2024), available at https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4904116, 27 and footnote 212.

¹²² *Bytedance* (n 113 above) paras 323–324.

¹²³ *Ibid.* para 327.

the failure to comply with an obligation. Following the logic of this paper, abandoning market definition is legitimate since harm to a collective interest is irrelevant to its implementation.

Moreover, harm to the market (as a representation of the collective interest) not only does not serve as working concept in the enforcement of the law, it is not even clear that it is part of the law's objectives. It can be queried whether the DMA is meant to protect the market (as a representation of the collective) directly or indirectly. Is the DMA's legislative justification the reduction of harm to the market (the collective) as a direct outcome, or is it meant to safeguard individual interests to indirectly benefit the common good? The DMA has two goals: fairness and contestability.¹²⁴ While fairness relates to redressing imbalances in power, the contestability objective is to ensure the ability of undertakings which are not gatekeepers to effectively overcome barriers to entry and expansion and challenge the (designated) gatekeepers on the merits of their products and services.¹²⁵ It is not evident to what extent the ability of companies to challenge the gatekeeper has to be linked to the collective interest in competitive markets discussed above¹²⁶ in order to justify the enforcement of the DMA.¹²⁷ The General Court's rejection in *Bytedance* of the link between the goals of the law and designation left this question unanswered.

Following the logic of this paper, the methodological and resource challenges which were raised prior to the adoption of the DMA are insufficient to justify abandoning market definition, from a legitimacy perspective. It is the fact that the law does not require harm to be enforced, which supports that the authority will not have to engage in a market definition exercise. The story does not truly end here, however, as some effects analysis may be required to assess the effectiveness and appropriateness of remedies,¹²⁸ at least if that appropriateness is to be judged by reference to their ability to ensure contestability of the market. Moreover, the legislator may need to engage in a delineation of markets to evaluate whether the DMA has achieved its objective, overall, of opening up markets. In that sense, the 'market' would play a legitimising role in the assessment of the DMA, as the legislator proposes and should evaluate the achievements

¹²⁴ Leaving aside the overarching goal of harmonisation.

¹²⁵ *Bytedance* (n 113 above) para 22 and 309; Digital Markets Act (n 108 above), Recital 32.

¹²⁶ See section III.A.. See discussion of the interpretative problems of contestability and fairness (in general, but also as conflicts between different parts of the DMA) in Alba Ribera Martínez, 'The DMA's Ithaca: Contestable and Fair Markets' (2023) 46(4) *World Competition* 432-434.

¹²⁷ Martínez dissects contestability and notes that this objective 'builds on the reductive perspective that economic operators different to the gatekeepers must be encouraged to enter these same markets in the future when offering similar competing product offerings' (see *ibid* 440.)

¹²⁸ See Digital Markets Act (n 108 above), Article 18; see Martínez (n 126 above) 431.

of the law by reference to the market. Whether the legislator ought to do so depends on the interpretation of the goals of the DMA.

Thus, the underlying rationale of the law plays a role in testing the 'rhyme and reason'¹²⁹ of both the law itself and the enforcement of it by the Commission (both in terms of scoping appropriate compliance measures and identifying and addressing infringement). This could even include a review of the designation process, with the question: did the designation by the Commission make sense given the harm the DMA is meant to address?

V. Conclusion

This article has tried to explain why market definition is necessary as a matter of substantive legitimacy of competition law. Market definition focuses the scope of analysis by providing the forum within which to establish the violation of the law (as discussed above). In doing so, it legitimises enforcement action by enabling the identification of its target. It makes something abstract - 'competition' in the 'market' - concrete, allowing authorities to discuss it and assess the impact on it in a manner analogous to discussing an individual who is the target in an enforcement action.

Section II introduced the key argument of this article: that the definition of a relevant market - and subsequent reference to the market in the substantive analysis - contributes to the legitimacy of competition law enforcement. The section first discusses, generally, the theory for the legitimacy of the application of a specific law and intervention by a specific authority. It then sets out how the 'market' can be the expression of this legitimacy in the enforcement of competition law. Since the underlying assumption of Section II (and the article as a whole) is that competition law protects the collective interest, Section III provided support for this assumption, reflecting on the collective interest in competitive markets and setting out how the law refers to the collective interest as an objective. Section IV therefore sets out the differences between various ways in which the market can be referred to in other laws, illustrating why these other laws may not need market definition as a matter of legitimacy, either because they primarily protect individual interests or because there is no need to evidence harm. It uses intellectual property laws the Digital Markets Act as examples.

This article intended to convince readers of two things. First, that the existing scholarship on market definition misses the point that market definition has value of itself. Second, at a time when there seems to be a crisis about the extent of the competences of competition authorities,

¹²⁹ Cf. wording used by Bostoen and Monti (n 121 above).

the reference to the 'relevant market' as representation of the collective interest may be a way to justify the applicability of competition law as opposed to other areas of law or policy.

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